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**Interconnected Nord-Est
Innovation Ecosystem**

Cross-Cutting Activity #4

**Education
& Lifelong Learning**

i NEST!

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i NEST Interconnected
Nord-Est Innovation
Ecosystem

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Cover image: Piero Dorazio - Next Generation, 1968

*The artist and the scientist, according to Dorazio, propose two different but parallel paths:
they broaden knowledge, working more for the future than for the present.*

*"I don't try to educate the viewer about the function of color,
but rather to complete my own education on its possibilities."*

(from "Piero Dorazio" by Maurizio Fagiolo dell'Arco - Officina Edizioni - Roma, 1966).

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1 Introduction

iNEST is the Innovation Ecosystem of the Northern-Eastern part of Italy (the so-called “NordEst”). Among the activities to be developed, a particular focus is dedicated the Cross-Cutting initiatives addressed to Education and Lifelong Learning.

The Objectives of the Cross-Cutting action “Education & Lifelong Learning” in the frame of iNEST are associated to the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that enable people to contribute to and benefit from an inclusive and sustainable future is a process based on two pillars:

- Education, to equip students with the skills they need to become active, responsible and engaged citizens,
- Lifelong Learning, which is a strategic instrument for implementing innovation into society, with special attention paid to SMEs.

The capability of developing an integrated view of Education and Lifelong Learning paths is the key-challenge individuated in the frame of iNEST. Such challenge will be faced by designing, managing and exploiting some pilot-actions and projects.

To do this, an excellent starting point is constituted, on one side, by the overview of current trends, needs and challenges for Companies and workers and for Academy, professors and students, which are deeply described in various documents covering both international and national scenarios, and, on the other side, by a detailed analysis of the several innovative Education and Lifelong Learning actions developed by the 9 Universities involved in iNEST Ecosystem.

This document collects all these information, in view of the creation of an iNEST Innovation Academy, with a comprehensive view both on Education and on Lifelong Learning.

2 International and local scenarios

The need to anticipate the evolution of the future jobs has been the driving force of various investigations, carried out by international Institutions [1-8]. Some of the key-results can be summarized as follows.

1 Europe, in the frame of a research, recently carried out by Mc Kinsley [8], is constituted by almost 1,100 local economies across the 27 EU countries plus the United Kingdom and Switzerland, and **has been demonstrated to be a patchwork of highly varied local labor markets** that have seen increasing geographic concentration of employment growth in the past. Forty-eight dynamic cities, which are home to 20 percent of Europe's population, generated 43 percent of Europe's GDP growth, 35 percent of its net job growth, and 40 percent of its population growth between 2007 and 2018. By contrast, 438 shrinking regions with 30 percent of the population, mostly in Eastern and Southern Europe, have declining workforces, older populations, and lower educational attainment. The remaining half of the population lives in a wide range of economies that have been largely stable, with modest job growth prior to the pandemic. The COVID-19 crisis ended years of strong employment growth marked by greater mobility. The crisis put up to 59 million European jobs, or 26 percent of the total, at risk in the short term, through reductions in hours or pay, furloughs, and permanent layoffs.

NordEst of Italy, i.e. the focus of iNEST Innovation Ecosystem, is included in the frame of stable economies, containing high tech manufacturing centers, diversified economies and tourism-based economies (Fig. 1), in perfect agreement with the premises adopted in building iNEST.

Figure 1 - Characterization of local labor markets, focus on Italy [8]

2 Once the economy recovers, **Europe may have a shortage of skilled workers**, despite a growing wave of automation. A key reason is the declining supply of labor: Europe’s working-age population will likely shrink by 13.5 million (or 4 percent) due to aging by 2030. Scenarios developed for the pace of automation adoption show that 22 percent of current work activities (equivalent to 53 million jobs) could be automated by 2030. A large share of potential job losses (if not all) could be compensated by job growth from sources such as technology, rising incomes, and investments in healthcare [8].

3 More than half of Europe’s workforce will face significant transitions. Automation will require all workers to acquire new skills. About 94 million workers may not need to change occupations but will especially need retraining, as technology handles 20 percent of their current activities. While some workers in declining occupations may be able to find similar types of work, 21 million may need to change occupations by 2030. The strongest job growth is projected in professional, scientific, and technical services as well as human health and social work, while the biggest decline could occur in manufacturing (Figs 2-3) [8]. The recent report of the World Economic Forum [4] individuated the jobs which are in a growing stage and will be more and more required (Table 1).

Figure 2 - Potential net job growth in EU-27, United Kingdom and Switzerland in midpoint automation scenario [8]

	Hours in 2018, billion	Change in number of hours 2018–30, %	Examples
Physical and manual skills	159	-18	Craft and technician skills Fine motor skills
Basic cognitive skills	76	-28	Basic literacy and numeracy Basic data input/processing
Higher cognitive skills	106	4	Quantitative and statistical skills Project management
Social and emotional skills	93	30	Interpersonal skills and empathy Teaching and training others
Technological skills	54	39	Advanced IT skills/programming Scientific R&D

Figure 3 – Demand for technological, social and emotional skills is expected to grow in Europe [8]

Increasing demand		Decreasing demand	
1	Data Analysts and Scientists	1	Data Entry Clerks
2	AI and Machine Learning Specialists	2	Administrative and Executive Secretaries
3	Big Data Specialists	3	Accounting, Bookkeeping and Payroll Clerks
4	Digital Marketing and Strategy Specialists	4	Accountants and Auditors
5	Process Automation Specialists	5	Assembly and Factory Workers
6	Business Development Professionals	6	Business Services and Administration Managers
7	Digital Transformation Specialists	7	Client Information and Customer Service Workers
8	Information Security Analysts	8	General and Operations Managers
9	Software and Applications Developers	9	Mechanics and Machinery Repairers
10	Internet of Things Specialists	10	Material-Recording and Stock-Keeping Clerks
11	Project Managers	11	Financial Analysts
12	Business Services and Administration Managers	12	Postal Service Clerks
13	Database and Network Professionals	13	Sales Rep., Wholesale and Manuf., Tech. and Sci. Prod.
14	Robotics Engineers	14	Relationship Managers
15	Strategic Advisors	15	Bank Tellers and Related Clerks
16	Management and Organization Analysts	16	Door-To-Door Sales, News and Street Vendors
17	FinTech Engineers	17	Electronics and Telecoms Installers and Repairers
18	Mechanics and Machinery Repairers	18	Human Resources Specialists
19	Organizational Development Specialists	19	Training and Development Specialists
20	Risk Management Specialists	20	Construction Laborers

Table 1: List of growing and declining jobs [4]

4 Newly created jobs will require more sophisticated skills (i.e. tertiary education) that are already scarce today (Fig. 4). Europeans frequently switch jobs, but they typically move from one growing occupation to another growing occupation or from one declining occupation to another declining occupation, with little crossover [8].

Figure 4 - Many of the jobs that employers might need to fill by 2030 require a higher level of skills [8]

5 Four broad imperatives stand out: addressing skills shortages; improving access to jobs in dynamic growth hubs, potentially through an increase in remote working; revitalizing and supporting shrinking labor markets (since 40% of Europeans will live in regions where jobs are declining over the coming decade); and increasing labor participation.

With reference to the economies characterizing NordEst, the challenges and priorities are summarized in Fig. 5, with key-issues addressed to re-skilling of workers, increasing education level and STEM skills, creating sector specific economic development by entrepreneurship and innovation, and improving quality of jobs.

Local labor markets in Europe face a range of different challenges and priorities.

 Share of population, 2018
 Predicted change in working-age population, 2018–30
 Share of potential employment growth, 2018–30

Priorities		
<p>High-tech manufacturing centers</p> <p> 2% </p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversify industry mix with more service-based sectors • Retrain employees in highly automatable jobs to meet demand for future skills • Increase educational attainment and STEM skills to continue developing and integrating innovative technologies 	
<p>Diversified metro and non-metro areas, tourism havens</p> <p> 21% </p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve connectivity through public and digital infrastructure • Create sector-specific economic development strategies to attract investment and seed higher-value-added sectors • Promote entrepreneurship and innovation • Improve quality of jobs in low-wage regions 	

Figure 5 – Local labor markets in Europe face a range of different challenges and priorities: focus on High-tech manufacturing centers, diversified metro and non-metro areas, tourism havens, which characterize NordEst region [8]

6 The nature of work has been changing through the impact of three long-term trends:

technological change, social transformation and the green transition. Some key issues have emerged, to be addressed to ensure better work for workers and employers alike: volatility in wages and the cost of living; divergence on the demand for flexibility; silent pandemic in well-being; an erosion of diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) gains; the need for a reskilling revolution. The answer to these issues can be found through the new standards of the “Good Work Framework” [9], based on the following objectives:

- promote fairness on wages and technology,
- provide flexibility and protection,
- deliver on health and well-being,
- drive diversity, equity and inclusion,
- foster employability and learning culture.

Three enablers will be key for making good work a reality for all:

- human-centric leadership,
- applying workforce technology thoughtfully
- improving reporting.

7 Schools must prepare today 's children for jobs that have not yet been created, for technologies that have not yet been invented, to solve problems that have not yet been anticipated. It will be a shared responsibility to seize opportunities and find solutions. Students will need to develop curiosity, imagination, resilience and self-regulation, and they will need to cope with failure and rejection, and to move forward in the face of adversity. Their motivation will be more than getting a good job and a high income; they will also need to care about the well-being of their friends and families, their communities and the planet. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has launched The Future of Education and Skills 2030 project, aimed at shaping a shared future built on the well-being of individuals, communities and the planet [10]. In the face of an increasingly volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous world, **education** can make the difference as to whether people embrace the challenges they are confronted with or whether they are defeated by them. And in an era characterized by a new explosion of scientific knowledge and a growing array of complex societal problems, it is appropriate that curricula should continue to evolve, perhaps in radical ways.

8 Education must take into account the current key challenges [10]:

- Climate change and the depletion of natural resources require urgent action and adaptation;
- Scientific knowledge is creating new opportunities and solutions that can enrich our lives, while at the same time fueling disruptive waves of change in every sector
- Financial interdependence at local, national and regional levels has created global value chains and a shared economy, but also pervasive uncertainty and exposure to economic risk and crises. Data is being created, used and shared on a vast scale, holding out the promise of expansion, growth and improved efficiency while posing new problems of cyber security and privacy protection.
- As the global population continues to grow, migration, urbanization and increasing social and cultural diversity are reshaping countries and communities.

Education has a vital role to play in developing the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that enable people to contribute to and benefit from an inclusive and sustainable future. Learning to form clear and purposeful goals, work with others with different perspectives, find untapped opportunities and identify multiple solutions to big problems will be essential in the coming years. OECD Education 2030 stakeholders have co-developed a "learning compass" that shows how young people can navigate their lives and their world (Fig. 6).

Helping individuals connect with new opportunities and prepare for the jobs of tomorrow is a common task for every region across the EU.

Figure 6 - The OECD Learning Framework 2030 [10]

3 The role and challenges for Universities

European Institutions, since 2017, started an investigation about on the ways to maximize the impact of investments in research and innovation, in order to introduce tools for “performance-based funding” of Universities [11]. This process led to the definition of the Renewed Agenda for the Modernisation of Higher Education e to the proposal of “Regional Innovation Impact Assessment” (RI2A). Such an assessment is focused on

1. Education and human capital development;
2. Research, technological development, knowledge transfer and commercialisation;
3. Entrepreneurship and support to enterprise development;
4. Regional orientation, strategic development and knowledge infrastructure.

The European Institute of Technology (EIT) will coordinate in 2021-2027 (in the frame of Horizon Europe) a dedicated action to support **Innovation Capacities of European Universities** [12-13]; this action will promote:

- Higher integration into innovation chains,
- More active role in local economies,
- Specialisation and differentiation strategies,
- Efficient cooperation with Companies,
- Development of entrepreneurial mindset in students and staff,
- Better management of digital transition.

Among the initiatives already activated, they are worth-mentioning

- The HEInnovate portal [14], developed to facilitate a self-evaluation of Universities in terms of Leadership and Governance, Organisational Capacity (Funding, People and Incentives), Entrepreneurial Teaching and Learning, Preparing and Supporting Entrepreneurs, Digital Transformation and Capability, Knowledge Exchange and Collaboration, Internationalisation, Measuring Impact.
- The European University Network Pilot, to support the setup of network among European Universities; e.g. Eurotech Universities [15], in the Engineering area, is supporting an international study programme with the goal of jointly shaping the engineering education of the future. It will be open not only to students enrolled at the partner universities, but also to engineers working in industry who are interested in life-long learning. The initiative will reinvigorate the symbiosis between society and technology together with various stakeholders and orient its programme towards human-centred engineering.

With specific reference to Italy, a detailed mapping, related also to European and International driving forces, has been described in the “Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Higher Education in Italy” report [16].

Policy practices related to the entrepreneurial and innovation agenda in higher education are developing all over Italy. Italy's strong and international business sector as well as natural and cultural amenities provide vast engagement opportunities for higher education institutions. A strategic approach at system level should capitalize on existing institutional initiatives and help develop them to generate more value for the economy and society. Only a long-term national strategy can support higher education engagement with the society and with the business and economic sectors. Promoting the entrepreneurial and innovation agenda can help Italy improve the overall performance of the higher education system, and of individual universities, in all regions.

This is the background of iNEST Innovation Ecosystem [17], whose fourth Cross-Cutting Activity (i.e. Education and Lifelong Learning), will address all the key-issues evidenced in the state of the art reported in these pages.

4 The current and future Education potential of iNEST

iNEST partnership involves all the 9 Higher Education Institutions of NordEst, which are listed and geographically located in Fig. 7. These Institutions are offering an enormous support to the territorial system, in terms of Education, Research and Technology Transfer, and Third Mission.

An impressive description of the effort given in terms of Education and Lifelong Learning is offered by Table 2, collecting key-figures of those Universities and the sum of them, representing the Education potential of iNEST.

All these Universities are continuously improving and innovating both contents and methodologies for teaching and training, in the frame of local, national and international projects (Annex A collects full details about them). A short review is offered below, adopting the classification elaborated by OECD [10] and evidenced in Fig. 8, with final Competencies associated to:

- Knowledge (Disciplinary, Inter-disciplinary, Epistemic, Procedural),
- Skills (Cognitive and meta-cognitive, Social & Emotional, Physical & Practical),
- Attitudes and Values (Personal, Social, Local, Global).

Figure 7 - iNEST Ecosystem and Universities involved

	iNEST	UNIBZ	UNITN	UNIUD	IUAV	UNIPD	UNIVE	UNIVR	UNITS	SISSA
Year of foundation	2022	1997	1962	1978	1926	1222	1868	1982	1924	1978
Number of students	152570	4488	16.656	15661	4621	65457	21.340	28.688	16710	289
Number of Professors	6350	160	797	612	123	2315	681	839	725	98
Number of Schools/Faculties	66	5	15	8	1	8	8	8	10	3
Total Degree Programs	676	28	71	79	11	198	57	78	142	12
Master Degree Programs	325	16	43	39	6	108	38	37	38	--
Bachelor Degree Programs	267	12	28	40	5	89	19	41	33	--
PhD Courses	145	8	18	16	1	41	20	16	13	12
Specialization Schools	169	0	1	22	1	67	1	43	34	--
Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives	272	5	7	27	21	61	37	88	24	2
Lifelong Learning Initiatives	131	4	4	9	7	66	6	28	5	2

Table 2 - Key-figures of iNEST Ecosystem and of the Universities involved

Figure 8 - OECD Classification of the path to achieve Competencies

Several teaching initiatives are addressed to improving **knowledge**, in most case with strong attention paid to inter- and trans-disciplinary paths, such as:

- Master Degrees and PhD programs offered in cooperation with other Universities (including universities of the iNEST consortium)
- Transitions Technologies Education paths, offering the opportunity to Master students of developing inter-disciplinary knowledge about Smart Infrastructures or Green Technologies
- Winter and Summer Schools
- Studium Generale, unitedbz and the Alliance for Teaching and Research for Sustainability in South Tyrol
- Winter and Summer Schools
- Information and Communication Technologies
- Sustainability
- Master Degree in Data Science and Scientific Computing with UNITS and UNIUD
- International Master in Physics of Complex Systems (with POLITO & ICTP)
- Junior Maths Days conference and specialized seminar series
- Sustainability and digitalization
- Minors (Asia, culture society and markets, Artistic Management, Social innovation management for smart communities, Environmental humanities, Tools for thinking, Senses, science, and cultural expression, Integrated sustainability)
- Blended Courses
- Project of extra-curricular activities

A relevant focus is given, by all Universities, to the development and enrichment of **skills** by the students. Some examples are available, such as:

- Studium Duale and Scholarships sponsored by the entrepreneurial association (Assoimprenditori Alto Adige)
- Courses and projects offered to high-school students to support the transition from high schools to University (Percorsi per le Competenze Trasversali e per l'Orientamento - PCTO)
- Challenge-based learning (e.g., Student & Company Sprint)
- Challenge Based Learning (CBL)
- Seminars and Courses dedicated to the analysis of personal Soft Skills
- Innovative Teaching Laboratories (Active Learning Lab, Design Thinking, Business Modelling, Social research, Storytelling and Public Speaking)
- Team-based learning (TBL)
- Group working in large classes
- Innovative tutoring (and training to tutoring) initiatives

They are worth mentioning also the activities related to strengthening **attitudes and values**, with several initiatives covering:

- Lifelong Learning
 - Individual courses
 - Lifelong Learning Courses (including on-line Lifelong Learning modules, developed at national and international level)
 - Life-Long Learning Courses offered by SMACT Competence Center
 - Micro-credential & Digital credential courses
 - Innovative on-line Lifelong Learning modules, developed at national and international level
 - PA 110 cum Laude project, in cooperation with Public Administration
 - Training course on the management of the entire life cycle of a building
 - Days of technical training on the Landscape
 - Advanced/Professional Development course
 - Continuing Education courses
 - Short Master Programmes
 - Erasmus+ Project USAGE ("Up-Skilling Agricultural Engineering in Europe")
 - Innovative one-year long specialization programs: Master in High Performance Computing (MHPC), Master in Science Communication (MCS)
 - Studium Generale and the Alliance for Teaching and Research for Sustainability in South Tyrol

- Gender equality
 - Equal opportunities and inclusion initiatives
 - Courses on gender balance, in cooperation with local Institutions
 - Awards to highlight the role of women in STEM disciplines
 - Gender equality initiatives (Women in Maths and Women in Physics to reverse imbalance in gender representation at academic & research levels in mathematics and physics)

- Development of learners and teachers communities
 - Learning Factory (Smart Mini Factory)
 - Communities of Practice
 - Contamination Lab Verona - ClabVerona
 - Competency Center
 - Teaching4Learning permanent Working Group
 - Participation to European alliance with a focus on innovative teaching

Improvement of Knowledge, achievement of Skills, development of Attitudes and values are in all Universities supported by **structural actions**, such as:

- Elaboration of a digital certification frame, describing skills and knowledge achieved by students, and based on the EU-recognized systems of Open Badge and Micro-Credentials,
- Development of innovative training tools, with national and international cooperation for the development of MOOCs, with existing agreement with the key providers of e-Courses,
- Set up of innovative hardware system for video-lessons, characterised by high interactivity and supporting increased learning efficiency,
- Pilot project for virtualization of ICT labs and of technological labs,
- Internal calls supporting innovative training initiatives, to be developed jointly by various Departments,
- Joint participation of various Universities to POT and PLS national programs, supporting the development and strengthening of Guidance Counselling and Tutoring initiatives,
- Participation of various Universities of iNEST to Higher Education Initiatives (HEIs) Calls, with related elaboration of self-evaluation on the above-mentioned HEInnovate portal [14],
- Participation to some of the European Institute of Technology (EIT) Knowledge & Innovation Communities (KICs).

5 Concluding remarks

The state of the art presented in these pages is certainly promising and encouraging. Effort of iNEST Universities on Education and Lifelong Learning issues is strong, highly motivated and with relevant attention paid to innovation. The list of activities, initiatives and projects is really impressive, but generates some challenges:

- developing the capability, in perfect agreement with the mission of iNEST Ecosystem, of sharing, improving, up-grading these excellent experiences among Universities,
- making available such experiences and tools to own students, but also to students still in high schools,
- opening new up-skilling scenarios for persons already involved in professional activities and jobs,
- contributing to exploiting of NordEst potential by making true a systemic vision of the overall Education path of persons, as shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 - Overall and integrated vision of Education path of persons

Such challenges will be faced by the Education & Lifelong Learning Working Group of iNEST, firstly on a “design” level (during 2023) and then going, in 2024 and 2025, to the implementation stage.

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Annex A

A.1 University of Bolzano

Key figures of University of Bolzano are collected in Table A1.

	UNIBZ
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1997
<i>Number of students</i>	4488
<i>Number of Professors</i>	160
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	5
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	28
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	16
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	12
<i>PhD Courses</i>	8
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	0
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	5
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	4

Table A1 - University of Bolzano: key figures

For more information:

https://www.unibz.it/assets/Documents/University/Numbers-Facts/2022_09_02_Facts-and-Figures_EN.pdf

The Free University of Bolzano is involved in several innovative Training & Education activities. Among them, it is worth mentioning the following initiatives.

Studium Duale and Scholarships sponsored by the entrepreneurial association (Assoimprenditori Alto Adige)

Since many years, the University of Bolzano is offering its Bachelor in Industrial Mechanical engineering as a dual study program (studio duale), i.e., students have the opportunity to combine studies and work (also thanks to the extension of the duration of the bachelor to 4 years). While this teaching format is rather common in German-speaking countries, the experience of the University of Bolzano is rather unique in Italy.

The first years is foreseen as a full time year at the University, while from the second year onward students can sign an employment contract with a company participating in the program or with a new one and spend one semester at the company (doing then only the exams at the University) and one semester at the university every year.

Learning by doing and projects combined with self-paced study and tutorship programs (company tutors and university tutors) are the success key of this teaching format. Next to the knowledge of the specific study programme, students acquire precious professional skills like team-working and problem solving. In addition, in order to increase the affordability of the university degree for all students (independently by their economic means), the university signed an agreement with Assoimprenditori Alto Adige for the financing, by some companies, of three-year scholarships to 10 students worth 10,000 euros each for those admitted with the highest scores. For more information, please see the website of the abovementioned bachelor program:

<https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/sciencetechnology/bachelor-industrial-mechanical-engineering/>

Courses and projects offered to high-school students to support the transition from high schools to University (Percorsi per le Competenze Trasversali e per l'Orientamento - PCTO)

The University of Bolzano offer both individual internships and short courses/group projects to high school students. The topics covered include: simulation of manual and automated assembly systems, eye tracking technologies for product development and production, industrial engineering tools and methods, small and mini hydropower solutions, Software/App development. For more information, please see <https://www.unibz.it/it/services/orientation/pcto/#Organism-2878> (available only in Italian or German).

Similarly, the University launched in 2010 the project Uni meets School, which allows students to try during their 4th-5th years of high school some short University-courses (in case of subsequent enrollment 2-3 ECTS of the courses attended are recognized to the students).

Finally, orientation days and lab visits are also organized by the different Faculties as well as by the University for high schools students.

Master Degrees and PhD programs offered in cooperation with other Universities (including universities of the iNEST consortium)

Considering its relatively recent foundation (1997) and small dimension, the University of Bolzano has designed several study programs (in particular Master Degrees and PhD programs) in cooperation with other Italian and foreign Universities. This model has several advantages, such as it allows to exploit the competencies available at the different universities avoiding at the same time duplications of the teaching offer (in closer universities), it allow students to experience different universities (and sometimes countries), it allows to reach critical mass of students on subject areas / degrees that if offered in many universities would not have such a critical mass, it allows universities to offer more degrees (the so called "requisiti minimi" are indeed easier to be fulfilled since more Universities are involved). At this respect, just to make a few examples:

- (i) the [Master in Viticulture, Enology and Wine Marketing](#), which foresees a common first year in Conegliano (one of the locations of the University of Padova) and then a second year at the University of Udine (curricula: "Research and development in enology" and "Research and development for a sustainable viticulture"), at the University of Verona (curricula "Economy and marketing in wine business", " Identity, typicality, terroir" and "New frontiers in viticulture and enology") or at the University of Bolzano (curriculum: Sustainable management of mountain viticulture within landscape valorization").
- (ii) the [Master in Environmental Management of Mountain Areas](#) offered thanks to the cross-border cooperation within the EUREGIO between the University of Bolzano and the University of Innsbruck.
- (iii) the [Master in Energy Engineering](#) jointly offered by the University of Bolzano and the University of Trento.
- (iv) the [PhD programme in Linguistics](#) offered in cooperation (convenzione) with the Universities of Verona and Marburg. Unibz has been sponsored for this PhD, in terms of fellowships, by EURAC research and the Regione Trentino Alto Adige.
- (v) the [PhD programme in Economics and Finance and in Management](#) which foresees cooperations with the University of Verona as well as many leading foreign universities.

Challenge-based learning (e.g., Student & Company Sprint)

The University of Bolzano has offered in cooperation with other partners some challenge-based learning extra-curricular courses, to foster group working, critical thinking and entrepreneurship skills of students. An interesting example at this respect is the "Students & Company Sprint", a five-day course organized by the NOI Techpark and the University of Bolzano in February 2022 (financed by the European Social Fund), in which three companies presented an innovation challenge that student teams had to solve following the Google Design Sprint Methodology, mentored by experts and scientists. Based on a self-assessment questionnaire based on the European Entrepreneurship Competence framework sent to students after this course, this course had an overall very positive effect on students' entrepreneurial competences. The highest effect was on the ability to "work with others". A case study on this course is in preparation and will be published soon in the portal with higher education cases [HEInnovate](#). New editions - also with other formats - are planned in the next few years.

Learning Factory (Smart Mini Factory)

The Smart Mini Factory lab (<https://smartminifactory.it/about-us/smart-minifactory/>) is a learning factory laboratory used for applied research and for teaching (both Bachelor and Master courses and life-long courses). It aims to study and simulate different modern and advanced concepts of production technologies and methods in the context of Industry 4.0, with particular attention to small and medium enterprises.

Since 2019, it has been included among the 31 best practices in the world in the book "Learning Factories Concepts, Guidelines, Best-Practice Examples" (Springer Verlag ISBN 978-3-319-92261-4). A virtual tour of the learning factory is available at this link <https://my.matterport.com/show/?m=7TJk9Z5eoBf>.

Every year the Smart Mini Factory offers to both engineers and technicians and high-school teachers a series of seminars and training courses on specific topics related to the application of Industry 4.0 methods and technologies in both manufacturing and construction companies (most of these courses are also financed by the European Social Fund). The catalogue of courses offered is available in the brochure: <https://smartminifactory.it/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/SMF-booklet-2021.pdf>

Erasmus+ Project USAGE ("Up-Skilling Agricultural Engineering in Europe")

The Erasmus+ Project USAGE sought to enable smart, sustainable and inclusive growth through up-skilling, innovative pedagogic approaches and access to experience. The partners of the project are: Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Technical University of Munich TUM and University of Bolzano. At each partner university, advanced university courses on topics related to smart farming have been developed and implemented. A key element of the project was also to encourage learning mobility between countries and disciplines -inspiring more engineers to choose a career within smart farming, and more agronomists to further specialize in technological subjects. More information are available at this link: <https://usage.projects.unibz.it/>

Masters and Lifelong Learning Courses

The University of Bolzano offers a wide set of 1st-2nd Level Masters and Lifelong Learning Courses designed in cooperation with key stakeholders.

Among the 1st-2nd Level Masters, it is worth to mention the following course:

- ANTROPOLAD (Ladin linguistics, literature and culture,) for teachers of Ladin in the schools of Trentino (<https://www.unibz.it/it/faculties/education/antropolad/>)
- Inclusive Pedagogy for primary and secondary school teachers in German and Italian (<https://www.unibz.it/it/faculties/education/teaching-children-special-needs/>);
- Sustainable Management of Geo-hydrological Risk in Mountain Areas (<https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/sciencetechnology/sustainable-management-geo-hydrological-risk-mountain-areas/>);
- Fire Safety Engineering (<https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/sciencetechnology/fire-safety-engineering/>);
- BEE: Building, Energy and Environment - CasaClima (<https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/sciencetechnology/master-in-bee-building-energy-and-environment/>).

Among the short courses, it worth to mention the following course/programs:

- The Smart Enterprise Qualification Program (financed by the European Social Fund), which includes courses on automation with programmable logic controllers (PLC), Industry 4.0, collaborative robotics, product development, axiomatic design, simulation with open source software, artificial intelligence and data management (<https://hct.projects.unibz.it/smart-enterprise-qualification-program-qualification-program-for-smart-companies/>).
- The course "InnovaTive CS teAchiNg methoDs to foster kEy coMpetences (TANDEM - 2021)", financed by the European Social Fund.
- The course "Management control and sustainability reporting: principles, standards and tools" that will be offered in Summer/Fall 2023.
- The course Open Foam, which seeks to introduce students OpenFOAM-CFD theory and software architecture.

Studium Generale, unitedbz and the Alliance for Teaching and Research for Sustainability in South Tyrol

Studium Generale is an interdisciplinary study program offered by the University of Bolzano to the general public, for those who wish to strengthen their knowledge in various fields. It allows students to get awarded 30 ECTS-credits (within three years' time). The modules offered (3 to 6 ECTS) vary from semester to semester and focus on a wide range of topics, from creativity and culture to technology, to social science, law and business, languages and cultures, sustainability, and communication. Some of the courses are also offered in cooperation with other South Tyrolean research institutes, such as the Philosophical-Theological School at Brixen and the members of the Alliance for Research and Teaching for Sustainability in South Tyrol. The Alliance groups key research institutes in South Tyrol (University of Bolzano, Eurac Research, Philosophical-Theological School, Laimburg, Fraunhofer Italia, Naturmuseum, Eco Research and Ökoinstitut) and seeks to bind common know-how, stimulate discussion on sustainable development goals (SDGs) topics, propose recommendations for action for individuals, companies and decision makers, and proactively engage in the sustainability debate in South Tyrol.

More information is available at this link: <https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/further-courses/studium-generale/>.

Finally, the University of Bolzano launched in 2016 in cooperation with institutions and voluntary associations a pilot project named unitedbz, which allows to some asylum seekers and refugees the opportunity to attend free of charge (as extracurricular students) the courses offered by unibz for four semester. More information is available at this link: <https://www.unibz.it/en/faculties/further-courses/unitedbz/>

Life-Long Learning Courses offered by SMACT Competence Center

The University of Bolzano contributes also to the life-long learning courses offered by the SMACT Competence Center, in particular with courses on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning and on Industry 5.0 and robotics. The full catalogue of courses is available at this link: <https://www.smact.cc/corsi-di-formazione> (only in Italian).

A.2 University of Trento

Key figures of University of Trento are collected in Table A2.

	UNITN
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1962
<i>Number of students</i>	16.656
<i>Number of Professors</i>	797
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	15
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	71
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	43
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	28
<i>PhD Courses</i>	18
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	1
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	7
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	4

Table A2 - University of Trento: key figures

The University of Trento is involved in five main innovative Training & Education actions:

Challenge Based Learning (CBL): a new way of doing research and education, CBL is a pedagogical approach through which learners are actively involved in identifying, analyzing, and designing a solution that solves a challenge on current problems and real issues. Furthermore, the School of Innovation (SOI-UniTn), the first in Italy, offers to a wide range of Learners the possibility to create their personalized program by combining multiple courses focusing on innovation and entrepreneurship in different fields.

Learners will get both comprehensive technical knowledge and a set of highly-appreciated soft skills such as communication, leadership, teamwork, problem-solving and more.

Team-based learning (TBL): a pedagogical strategy that engages student knowledge acquisition through a combination of individual testing and group collaboration.

In TBL, (a) most of class time is organized with students working in permanent, strategically formed teams; (b) concept coverage is achieved through students' pre-class individual self-study followed by an in-class Readiness Assurance Process that involves both individual and team tests; (c) during team assignments, students help one another to learn course material at an applied level; and (d) students are accountable to one another through the use of a peer-assessment and feedback process. The TBL is used experimentally in some STEM courses.

Group working in large classes - collaborative learning groups are used in classes with more the 100 students. Procedures, problems, solutions, and evaluations are experimentally applied in several courses. obtaining an increase of average outcome evaluation.

Communities of Practice - six groups of teachers who share experiences working together in a way that embodies the spirit of collaboration. The community of practice is important because it connects teachers who might not have the opportunity to interact, provide a shared context, enable dialogue, and capture and diffuse existing knowledge.

Micro-credential & Digital credential courses - flexible, inclusive learning opportunities are systematically offered to UniTN students and external professionals. A total of 16 micro/digital credentials has been activated.

A.3 University of Udine

Key figures of University of Udine are collected in Table A3.

	UNIUD
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1978
<i>Number of students</i>	15661
<i>Number of Professors</i>	612
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	8
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	79
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	39
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	40
<i>PhD Courses</i>	16
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	22
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	27
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	9

Table A3 - University of Udine: key figures

University of Udine is involved in several innovative Training & Education activities. Among them, they are worth mentioning:

Continuous Learning - Training activities on Communication (Transparency, Efficiency, Digital Skills). The aim of these courses is to create a new awareness on the topic of the effectiveness and simplification of institutional communication, web and social communication, digital skills, strategic elements in the renewal process of the Public Administration or of the companies.

The training project looks mainly at the professional figures with a view to their professional updating in the thematic framework of institutional communication with particular regard to the new challenges and opportunities offered by the Digital Agenda.

Winter and Summer Schools - Several summer and winter schools are organized for continuous training of PhD students and employees of local manufacturing companies such as:

- (a) Summer School "Introduction to renewable energies - SIER",
- (b) Summer School on "Orienting oneself in thought: philosophy and digital worlds",
- (c) Winter School on "Winter Monitoring Techniques of Homeothermic Alpine Fauna",

- (d) Summer School - Designing and testing new development models in the human-animal-environment interdependence. Agroecology, social inclusion, territory and community,
(e) Summer school on "Artificial Intelligence: from Deep Learning to Data Analytics".

PA 110 cum Laude project - PA 110 cum laude is a project launched by the Ministry of Public Administration as part of the broader plan called "Re-Formare" the Public Administration. PA 110 cum laude intends to enhance university vocational training, to enable public employees who have graduated to obtain a university degree. Specific study programs are also planned for targeted training in the Public Administration's fields of interest. In this context, the University of Udine signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Ministry for Public Administration to offer, as early as February 2022, the opportunity for PA employees to enroll in study courses with a specific focus on PA. For the academic year 2022/23, bachelor's and master's degree courses and advanced and refresher courses will be part of the program. The training offer is designed to meet the goal specified in the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Component 1-Mission 1) of developing interventions to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of processes by strengthening the skills of human capital in administrations.

Individual courses - Enrolment in individual courses allows students to attend lectures, sit for the final exam of one or more subjects of the various degree courses or single-cycle degree courses offered at University of Udine and obtain a certificate. These are one of the initiatives aimed at encouraging continuing education and are aimed at those who want to update themselves on specific topics or supplement their professional skills; - have already graduated but need additional examinations for admission to public competitions or specialization courses; need to acquire the curricular requirements for admission to a Master's degree course; wants to obtain recognition of examinations upon enrolment in a degree course.

Equal opportunities and inclusion - The course aims to promote a culture of respect and inclusion. Specifically, the course aims to acquire knowledge on the systemic mechanisms of exclusion and make people understand the genesis of stereotypes and prejudices; develop skills to promote equal opportunities, the inclusion of diversity, the recognition and enhancement of different talents in a logic of promotion of rights, respect and civil coexistence, reduction of inequalities and the fight against all forms of discrimination and violence; promote autonomy of judgement, mediation skills, adaptation, integration and inclusion; develop soft skills aimed at managing and communicating the value of diversity in professional contexts and in team working.

The course is structured along interdisciplinary lines and involves lecturers from all the University's departments. The topics of gender, diversity inclusion and equal opportunities are developed according to a multidisciplinary approach and in an interdisciplinary perspective. The involvement of lecturers belonging to different scientific-disciplinary fields makes the course varied and stimulating. The method used by the lecturers is that of dissemination of the results of scientific research in order to make concepts and notions from each discipline accessible to all, focusing more on perspective and message than on technicalities.

A.4 University of IUAV

Key figures of University of IUAV are collected in Table A4.

	IUAV
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1926
<i>Number of students</i>	4621
<i>Number of Professors</i>	123
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	1
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	11
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	6
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	5
<i>PhD Courses</i>	1
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	1
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	21
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	7

Table A4 - University of IUAV: key figures

Alongside the themes and subjects that characterize each specific degree program (Architecture, Urban Planning, Design, Arts), the IUAV University of Venice has structured initiatives aimed at the transversal training of its students on relevant topics that are fundamental to face the future challenges of the territories.

Information and Communication Technologies and the theme of *Sustainability* have been identified as relevant topics to improve the competence and the skills of its students.

The University offers elective courses that focuses and /or involve ICT or Sustainability topics. Many of them are transversal to all study programs.

Regarding *Sustainability*, elective courses are about:

- Maritime spatial planning;
- Geography of global supply chains;
- History of contemporary architecture;
- Design of Common Goods and Co-design of urban spaces.

Regarding *ICT*, elective courses are about:

- Digital interactions;
- Drawing laboratory, animation and digital scene

In addition to the training on specific topics and skills relevant to the innovation of the territory, the traditional teaching is integrated with activities aimed at strengthening the students' soft skills.

For this reason, among the various job placement initiatives, the IUAV University promotes the organization of workshops, seminars and meetings that aim to help students identify and certify their skills. These training sessions are preparatory to improving the job search process following graduation.

The theme is addressed in various types of events, including a series of seminars dedicated to the analysis of personal Soft Skills. The activity is organized through a mix of lectures and workshops which, with innovative methodologies such as Serious Play, aim to support participants in bringing out their thoughts, their strengths, Soft Skills and their relational and communication skills.

There are also meetings dedicated to building and improving one's transversal skills necessary to live and work in an international environment.

To improve the impact of university research and its competences on the territory, it is necessary that the training and research activity is not aimed exclusively at students, but that it involves the territory and the professionals that operate in it.

On this aspect, recently, during the a.y. 2022/23, IUAV has designed a training course on the management of the entire life cycle of a building (with regard to the health sector) aimed at personnel of the ULSS 3 Serenissima (health department of the Venice area). Through this advanced training course, methodologies and techniques are analysed, explored and implemented, in order to get the competences and skills to manage an advanced "organizational model" by the use of innovative tools that allow to govern activities, flows and products of the operational phases of building construction: launch, management and control of procedures of tender; monitoring and control of the construction stages of the work; monitoring and control of the management and maintenance activities of the works; functional and spatial variations/variants of building parts. The model presented in this course is based on a pervasive use of ICT tools such as BIM softwares.

Among this innovative course and the well-established training activities, the University offers the "Giornate di formazione tecnica sul paesaggio" (Days of technical training on the Landscape).

It is a professional training course, active since 2018, organized in synergy with the Regional Observatory for the Veneto landscape. This training initiative is aimed at professionals (engineers, architects, urban planners, agronomists/foresters, geologists, agrotechnicians) and public administration technicians, as well as farmers who carry out their activity in traditional rural landscapes or in agricultural lands that are characterized of historical interest that feature the territory of the Veneto Region. The aim of the course, even if it focalized in the Veneto territory, is to provide the knowledge and technical skills to promote the protection, management and redevelopment of the landscapes of the Northeast of Italy, with particular attention to territorial, urban and sector planning policies and to those of a cultural, environmental, agricultural, social and economic.

A.5 University of Padova

Key figures of University of Padova are collected in Table A5.

	UNIPD
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1222
<i>Number of students</i>	65457
<i>Number of Professors</i>	2315
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	8
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	198
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	108
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	89
<i>PhD Courses</i>	41
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	67
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	61
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	66

Table A5 - University of Padova: key figures

University of Padova is involved in several innovative Training & Education activities, which are structured at various levels.

The *central unit* for improving and modernizing teaching at Padua University is constituted by the **Teaching4Learning@Unipd®** project. Through project courses, teachers will become part of departmental and inter-departmental communities where they can initiate and share good teaching practices and promote innovative, technological methods. Teaching4Learning@Unipd® is the result of constant research carried out in the field of teaching in higher education and in international research groups that propose as their ultimate objective the innovation of university teaching. They aim to do so by promoting learner-centered approach, aligning with the proposals of European documents: Strategy 2020 (European Commission, 2010) and the Agenda for the modernization of the European higher education system. The teachers voluntarily involved in the project are highly interested and motivated, with a significant driver to share their experience with other colleagues. In fact, at the end of the proposed training course, the expected result concerns the chance of creating a faculty learning community among the participants, with the aim of being able to support each other in teaching practices and experimenting with and discovering together new teaching strategies to engage students, encouraging active and informed participation in teaching activities.

The *methodologies and techniques* through which university teaching is carried out are often complemented by the strategic use of technology. In response to this need, the **Digital Learning and Multimedia** (DLM) office has set up a web page dedicated to the use of new technologies for teaching, where are indicated: tools and courses available for teaching, guides and tutorials on the use of the various tools, services to support the University staff, possibility of requesting workshops and specific training activities, according to the needs of schools or departments (in recent years, weekly workshop cycles have already been provided on the use of Moodle and new technologies for teaching).

In order to improve its *presence at international level*, the University of Padova has decided to join the **MOOC** world and to produce some courses held in English, as part of a new strategy on education and distance learning where innovative pedagogical techniques are needed. With FutureLearn for Campus, the whole University of Padova community can access Future Learn's MOOCs or enjoy for free the upgraded versions of courses from institutions that have joined. Special devices to improve teaching and learning efficiency have been developed (e.g. the patented LightBoard, see <https://www.boardonair.eu/>).

An intensive programme courses addressing **students** at developing **cross and soft skills** is available. Skills and abilities acquired by participating in projects, training courses and/or other activities in the various areas of university life, in order to promote an inclusive university environment are certified. Some examples are: Communication and Soft Skills, Digital Skills - Psychology, Formula SAE International Competition - Operative Member and Executive Member, JEst - Junior Enterprise, Mooc Probability and Statistics, MotoStudent International Competition, Lift UP - Aircraft Design for the ACC student competition, Design of Components in a Critical Raw Materials Perspective, 1001Vela Cup International Project - Mètis Vela Unipd, RAIDMAP - Raw Ideas for Materials Projects, Scientific Communication for Psychology (SC4P), Soft Skills for Management, Soft skills for personal and professional development, Formative tutoring, UniZEB Operative Member, Valorisation of the University's Cultural Heritage. For **teaching staff**, training courses are also offered, to improve teaching through the adoption of innovative teaching techniques and by involving students through experimental proposals: Inclusive teaching, Teaching online, Mooc Educator, Mooc Lead Educator, Peer Observation, Teaching4Learning, Teaching4Learning Change Agent, Teaching Online.

Coming to **Disciplinary projects to enhance teaching quality**, since 2018 UNIPD has financed the implementation of innovative teaching projects to foster the improvement of teaching in undergraduate, master's and single-cycle master's degree courses.

Projects are presented by Schools or by Departments, and include initiatives for the improvement of teaching that can directly involve students with proposals for innovation and experimentation in teaching. Virtual labs (technological & informatics, see <https://vlab.unipd.it/>) have been developed, as well as innovative international tutoring initiatives, industrial seminars, wide programs multi- and inter-disciplinary courses, pilot project on blended courses. .

In the area of Engineering, the pilot-project **Transitions Technologies** has been developed, offering new approaches to face multi-dimensional problems associated to ecological and digital transitions. New education paths, integrated with existing Master Degree programs, have been set up, to shape two modern professional profiles, such as those of Green Technologies Expert and Smart Infrastructures Expert (<https://ingegneria.unipd.it/didattica/transitions-technologies#>).

Several Master Degree programs (upgraded or recently introduced) are also covering key topics such as **sustainability and digitalization**, e.g.: Sustainable Chemistry and Technologies for Circular Economy, Environmental Engineering, Sustainable Agriculture, Data Science, Management for sustainable firms, Tourism, culture and sustainability, Energy engineering, Cybersecurity.

A relevant focus, at different levels, is given to **continuous and lifelong learning** initiatives, including Specialization Schools, First-level and Second-level Short Specialization degrees (quite advanced scientific courses or studies in life-long learning programs, with acquisition of at least 60 credits), Higher level training courses, Professional courses. In several cases, such initiatives are developed in cooperation with Public Administration (e.g. PA 110 cum Laude project, in cooperation with Public Administration) or in the frame of EU projects (e.g. LightRight, 4LAlloys and MILLE Projects, all financed by EIT-RM and covering topics related to sustainability and eco-sustainable design).

Furthermore, University of Padua has adopted **open badges and digital certificates** so that the skills acquired in the various academic fields can be tracked and promoted. In this way, each training path can be certified and becomes part of the know-how of students and UNIPD staff, ensuring their personal and professional growth. Both open badges and blockcerts-digital certificates are digital certifications. issued to meet the need to develop digital solutions which comply with national and international policies.

A.6 University of Venezia Ca' Foscari

Key figures of University of Venezia Ca' Foscari are collected in Table A6.

	UNIVE
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1868
<i>Number of students</i>	21.340
<i>Number of Professors</i>	681
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	8
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	57
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	38
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	19
<i>PhD Courses</i>	20
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	1
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	37
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	6

Table A6 - University of Venezia Ca' Foscari: key figures

Ca' Foscari University has established a "Teaching & Learning Innovation Center" which aggregates within a single hub all the University initiatives related to teaching innovation, the development of methodologies and tools for a better learning and teaching experience, training transversal skills and soft skills. The center **designs and delivers** several innovative Training & Education activities.

Among them, those that are worth mentioning are: **blended courses**, **minors**, the **innovative teaching laboratories** and the **Competency Center**.

BLENDED COURSES

Blended training means adopting an approach that combines traditional training with trainer-led online activities. Unlike eLearning, online classes do not completely replace face-to-face classes; teachers use technology to enrich the learning experience and expand knowledge. The first Blended courses at Ca' Foscari started in the a.y. 2013/14 with the SxA (Studiare per Apprendere) project. The number of courses that apply this modality has never been significant, if compared to the overall training offer, but the feedback, as far as student satisfaction is concerned, has always been very positive.

MINORS

The Minors are a complementary path to the degree courses, which allows to enrich the student's main field of training with transversal skills useful for both continuing their studies and meeting the demands of the world of work. Each Minor consists of three courses of 6 credits each. After passing the three exams that make up the Minor, students obtain a certificate of the path taken and an Open Badge: a digital certification that describes the skills acquired.

Examples of interdisciplinary Minors

Asia, culture society and markets

The three modules that embrace the four macro-areas covered by the course - China, Japan, the Middle East and the Indian subcontinent - are aimed at students from the scientific, economic, cultural-humanistic fields who intend to direct their cultural and professional attention towards the countries of Asia. The purpose of this Minor course is to allow students not specialised in the languages and cultures of those areas to approach a variety/plurality of ways of life, thought and communication, typical of some regions (macro-areas) of Asia, providing them with basic knowledge to understand individual and collective customs and behaviour, work and organization systems in the context of companies, markets, businesses, academic and research institutions.

Artistic Management

Through the Minor in Artistic Management students learn and apply the techniques of artistic expression, increasingly requested by companies for their storytelling but also to introduce and strengthen the cultural variable in the workplace. This responds to the growing interest of companies in managerial figures with transversal skills, possessing both creative and technical knowledge. The Minor proposes a new idea of manager, aware of the resources offered by the languages of art.

Social innovation management for smart communities

The changes in the social and economic ecosystem provide a reliable key to understanding the increasingly numerous cases of governance failure, both of companies and institutions. Management, in rethinking its own paradigms and value system from the ground up, must resize the traditional techno-centric approach and contaminate itself with contributions from the humanities and social disciplines, to place people and society at the centre of the value system.

Environmental humanities

This Minor intends to introduce BA students to a new academic area that addresses the urgent planetary environmental crisis from an interdisciplinary perspective.

It sheds light on the cultural dimensions of the ecological crisis, interpreting them from a both critical and creative perspective: the dialogue between literature, history, anthropology, philosophy, linguistics, cinema, arts, social sciences and natural sciences. Ca' Foscari boasts the first master's degree in EH in Italy and a dedicated research centre, thus already being able to offer possible outlets and further intellectual stimuli to those who follow the Minor.

Tools for thinking

This Minor provides students of all degree courses (particularly in economics and science) with some basic epistemological and philosophical-linguistic tools, specifically related to methodological and operational aspects of the respective areas. To facilitate the application and demonstrate the usability of the theoretical tools to which students will be introduced, in each module the purely philosophical analysis is accompanied by examples, thought experiments and case studies in various fields of work and research.

Senses, science, and cultural expression

The aim of the Minor is to provide the foundations and demonstrate how the development of scientific knowledge on human perception based on sight, hearing, smell and taste is reflected in different fields, ranging from art to technology. In particular, it presents how recent knowledge in the fields of physics and chemistry allow to reproduce and manipulate sounds, images, smells and flavors, both for creative/aesthetic purposes and to improve the quality of everyday life and/or overcome sensory and perceptual disabilities.

Integrated sustainability

The objectives of the Minor are to propose a path in the direction of integrated sustainability, using a practical-experiential method, based on the discussion with those who are trying to implement this new approach in the various fields, but also on a laboratory proposal, in which to experience what 'practice' sustainability' means.

INNOVATIVE TEACHING LABORATORIES

Innovative teaching laboratories include Contamination Lab (CLab) and Active Learning Lab (ALL). These laboratories are organized by a theme, chosen by the University in collaboration with partners. They are normally organized over 6-8 weeks, for a total of 150 hours of activities, which include interactive teaching sessions, group work, review activities and presentation of results. Part of the hours foreseen in the laboratory are dedicated to autonomous group work to achieve the weekly objectives. The participants (high school students, university students and graduates) are divided into groups, according to the criteria of interdisciplinarity, gender, transversal skills and thematic preferences expressed.

The **Active Learning Lab** (ALL) and the **Ca' Foscari Contamination Lab** (CLab) are organised in specific laboratories lasting 6/8 weeks with the aim of accompanying university students and graduates from different disciplinary backgrounds, in a process of developing original projects on real challenges and problems, through the enhancement of their creativity, by using innovative methodologies such as Design Thinking and Business Model Canvas.

Teaching methods

Design Thinking

A methodology for group innovation developed by Stanford University, promotes creativity and collaboration between disciplines and allows the exploration and reformulation of problems starting from people's needs, fosters empathy and creative trust, to overcome the failure.

Business Modelling

Participants are invited to outline the logic behind the value of a company, i.e. the strategy that the entrepreneur develops to make a profit by providing value to his customers. According to the classic definition, the business model "describes the logic with which an organization creates, distributes and captures value".

Social research

Transmission of the basics of social research on consumption: theories on the subject, concrete examples of research and a synthesis of the qualitative-quantitative methodologies that can be used. Implementation of field research follows, both to test what was said in the first part and to find useful data for students' proposals.

Storytelling and Public Speaking

Communicating effectively means knowing how to express oneself in every situation with any interlocutor, both verbally and non-verbally (facial expressions, voice and posture), clearly and consistently with the message we want to convey. Public speaking is the discipline that provides the communication tools and strategies that allow a speaker to explain concepts in front of an audience in a clear and effective way.

Examples of recent innovative teaching labs

- The Memory of Ice
- Venetia Metaversa Bvlgari

THE CA' FOSCARI COMPETENCY CENTER

The Ca' Foscari Competency Center (CFCC) carries out research, training and consultancy activities for the development and assessment of transversal skills or soft skills.

Its mission is to increase people's performance and their attractiveness on the labour market through the development of their soft skills. The Center is aimed at companies and individual professionals by offering:

- Career Labs
- Training on specific emotional and social skills
- Development paths

The training courses are customized according to the recipients (individual professionals or companies) and allow participants to acquire methods and tools based on the Intentional Change Process approach. Unlike traditional training courses for the development of skills, this methodological approach allows participants to achieve a lasting and sustainable change in their portfolio of skills.

A.7 University of Verona

Key figures of University of Verona are collected in Table A7.

	UNIVR
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1982
<i>Number of students</i>	28.688
<i>Number of Professors</i>	839
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	8
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	78
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	37
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	41
<i>PhD Courses</i>	16
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	43
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	88
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	28

Table A7 - University of Verona: key figures

The University of Verona is involved in several innovative Training & Education Courses. Among them, some of those that are worth mentioning in relation to the project are:

Advanced/Professional Development course

- Corso di perfezionamento in Management economico-finanziario dell'ente locale
- Corso di perfezionamento e aggiornamento professionale in Training project specialist
- Esperto in progettazione finanziata regionale e nazionale

Continuing Education courses

- Corso di formazione continua in Employability development programme - Mappatura, valutazione e implementazione di competenze a sostegno dell'occupabilità

Short Master Programmes

- Master in Logistica & supply chain management
- Master in Computer game development

Degree Programmes:

- Laurea magistrale interateneo in Viticoltura, enologia e mercati vitivinicoli
- Laurea magistrale in Artificial Intelligence
- Laurea magistrale in Biotecnologie agro-alimentari
- Laurea magistrale in Biotecnologie per le biorisorse e lo sviluppo ecosostenibile
- Laurea magistrale in Computer Engineering for Robotics and Smart Industry
- Laurea magistrale in Data Science

Moreover, the University of Verona, promotes innovative action, in the framework of **interdisciplinary and transversal processes**, dedicated to different audiences: students (from high school to post graduate), professionals, and university professors.

Contamination Lab Verona - CLab Verona - is dedicated to undergraduates, graduates, PhD students of the University of Verona. This project allows them to participate in an interdisciplinary and transversal project that uses non-traditional teaching methods and involves the use of innovative technologies, highly qualified skills, and specialist instruments present in laboratories and research centres. Clab promotes training modules dedicated to innovation and business culture with the aim to develop problem solving, team building, and analysis of business and market opportunities in participants, linked to specific needs proposed by partners.

In particular, CLab Verona offers the opportunity to participate in: CLab Marathon (laboratory activities in which students work in groups directly on the premises of the company or organization that launched the challenge), and CLab Plus (activities developed by alternating meetings with experts and trainers and group work to solve the challenges posed by companies or institutions).

Furthermore, the University of Verona promotes and supports collaboration with companies and local authorities through initiatives that involve the use of innovative technologies such as the participation in Business Plan Competitions, i.e., **Start Cup Veneto**.

In the framework of transversal skills, activities are organised within:

- the **Teaching and Learning Center - TaLC** - of the University of Verona, that promotes training courses for students enrolled in degree courses, aimed at building skills that are useful both from a personal and work point of view and from a civic engagement point of view. The training courses are linked to nine areas: numeracy, literacy, problem solving, civic, digital, environmental, personal and interpersonal, health, financial. Within this centre every semester there are several courses for students. At this moment there are 34 available courses on a wide variety of topics built for students from all disciplines. Participation in the course is recognized as an educational activity and the students receive Open Badge, digital certificates which certify the possession of disciplinary knowledge, personal soft skills, and technical skills.

TaLC is also involved in organizing and promoting training sessions dedicated to university professors to support them in the continuous improvement of the didactic action, focused on active learning, e-learning, innovative teaching methods.

TaLC also organises 'Service learning' activities where students are involved in local realities with the aim of supporting them in solving open problems.

- T-the PlayLab@UniVR project, whose aim is to organise playful, experiential and interactive training workshops which will allow students and graduates of the university to develop their transversal skills and increase their potential. The project is linked to four areas of expertise: Powered (decision making and entrepreneurship), Leader (emotional intelligence and ability to motivate), Accurate (problem solving, critical and divergent thinking), Easy (collaboration and customer orientation).
- In this framework, the University of Verona promotes projects also dedicated to *High School students* for the achievement of transversal skills and for the development of the ability to orient oneself in personal life and reality, by improving knowledge, skills and competences, from a personal, civic, social and employment perspective.

The University of Verona also pays attention to **the gender enrolment gap** with dedicated projects. At the aggregate level, female students make up 65% of students enrolled in the years 2017-2020. This data is higher than the corresponding Italian aggregate ones, which for the 2019-2020 sees the female component be around 56% of the total (a.y. 2019-2020). Nevertheless, the proportion of students enrolled by gender considerably changes in the different areas of study and the female rate is low for engineering, manufacturing and construction, information and communication technology areas. Therefore, the University of Verona promotes initiatives aimed at showing that scientific-technological activities (STEM) are not only a male prerogative but a matter of effective interest and passion. In this framework, the project **NERD? Non E' Roba per Donne?** aims to arouse or strengthen the interest of all female students of secondary school institutions, in Verona and its province, towards future scientific-technological activities. It is a project also aimed at female students who have not chosen a scientific/technological path during the upper secondary school.

A.8 University of Trieste

Key figures of University of Trieste are collected in Table A8.

	UNITS
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1924
<i>Number of students</i>	16710
<i>Number of Professors</i>	725
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	10
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	142
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	38
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	33
<i>PhD Courses</i>	13
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	34
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	24
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	5

Table A8 - University of Trieste: key figures

University of Trieste has several Training & Education activities both integrated in the courses of first, second and post-graduate level both in specific, transversal and extracurricular activities.

Courses - University of Trieste offers courses in the fields of social-humanistic studies, of science and technology, and of life and health sciences. Several courses deal with the themes of sustainability and digitalization; in particular the following master's degrees are worthy of mention:

- "Economy, environment and development",
- "Materials and chemical engineering for nano, bio, and sustainable technologies",
- "Data science and artificial intelligence",
- "Geophysics and geodata",
- "Global change ecology and sustainability".

Post-graduate offer - Among the post-graduate offer, University of Trieste activates several advanced master, specialization and professional development courses. Of particular interest for this project are interdisciplinary and innovative courses as the Advanced Masters in Sustainable blue economy and Medical Physics, and the professional development course in Health humanities. Furthermore, the University of Trieste activates Summer and Winter Schools open to international students and addressing topics ranging from inclusion and cultural relations to the new challenges emerging from energy technologies.

PA 110 cum Laude project - To promote the Life Long-Learning University of Trieste has also activated the PA 110 cum Laude project, in cooperation with Public Administration, favoring the enrolment of public employees in almost all its courses.

European Alliance - The University of Trieste is partner of an European Alliance, that has the objective to promote the development of competencies to deal with emergent global transformations (digital infrastructure, environmental sustainability and social inclusion), through innovative challenge-based curricula.

Teaching Learning Center - With the aim to activate in medium term a **Teaching Learning Center**, the University of Trieste has recently completed a pilot project, called "Trasformazione", for the improvement, sharing and innovation of the teaching skills of its teachers.

Specific activities are the following:

Open Badge project - In order to enrich its educational offer, to increase students' skills and competences and to provide a tool to improve their curriculum, University of Trieste has started a project of extracurricular activities aimed at issuing Open Badges hosted by the Italian digital credentialing platform Bestr; these Open Badges to certificate disciplinary knowledge, transversal skills, linguistic and IT skills, professional technical are awarded to student's extracurricular activities even if their ex-post recognition remains possible. There are a variety of subject areas introducing badges, and the number of Open Badges awarded by the University of Trieste is steadily increasing. Some of University of Trieste Open Badges currently available are:

- "Occupational safety and health",
- "Individual creativity techniques",
- "Business management: startup with Leadership, Teambuilding & Intellectual property".

C-Lab project - The Contamination Lab represents, for the students, the opportunity to unleash their creativity, develop their entrepreneurial spirit and managerial potential so as to work on their own projects and grow professionally; in order to deliver its mission, the C-Lab is structured on four services:

- *learning* (innovative training courses);
- *mentoring* (a service dedicated to the support of innovative enterprises and start-up);
- *coworking* (an exclusive space where students can work on their project and share ideas);
- *making corner* (specific area equipped with instruments as 3D printers and laser cutters to develop prototypes).

A.9 SISSA

Key figures of SISSA are collected in Table A9.

	SISSA
<i>Year of foundation</i>	1978
<i>Number of students</i>	289
<i>Number of Professors</i>	98
<i>Number of Schools/Faculties</i>	3
<i>Total Degree Programs</i>	12
<i>Master Degree Programs</i>	--
<i>Bachelor Degree Programs</i>	--
<i>PhD Courses</i>	12
<i>Specialization Schools</i>	--
<i>Masters & Post-Lauream Initiatives</i>	2
<i>Lifelong Learning Initiatives</i>	2

Table A9 - SISSA: key figures

SISSA is one of the seven schools of excellence in Italy dedicated to advanced doctoral training and, in particular, the first Italian institution ever to award PhDs. It is located in Trieste, one of Europe's main scientific hubs: over 30 research centers present in the area and the highest number of researchers pro capita of any European city.

The core business of SISSA is in its PhD programs and their contribution to research including in partnership with industries. An exceptional feature of our PhD scholarships is that they last for four years: students select their PhD projects at the end of the first year in which their main duty is to follow research level courses. This setting gives them a broader view of their research area and, at the same time, provides them with a solid high-level knowledge of their research field.

Importantly, this opportunity is made available to PhD students from any awarding institution through the the Visiting students Training Programs (VSTP) in Mathematics and Physics.

SISSA also participates in innovative higher education programs funded by the Pnrr. It is partner in two new Pnrr National Doctorate programmes:

- *Space Science and Technology* (lead by UNITN)
- *Theoretical and Applied Neuroscience* (lead by UNICAM)

SISSA does not run its own Bachelor or Master degrees. However, it is involved in a few cross-institutional and transversal MSc level programs in partnership with other iNEST institutions. Relevant to iNEST is, for instance, the Laurea Magistrale in *Data Science and Scientific Computing* with UNITS and UNIUD, followed up by the recently established PhD programme in *Theoretical and Scientific Data Science* (TSDS). SISSA also partners at the international level to the training of high skilled scientists in high priority sectors such as with the *International Master in Physics of Complex Systems* (with POLITO & ICTP) and the pan-European HPC Master program (see below).

SISSA runs two innovative one-year long specialization programs:

- *Master in High Performance Computing* (MHPC) in collaboration with ICTP. An innovative specialization course covering the fast-growing field of high performance computing (HPC) which includes lecturers from the industrial world. Since 2021, the MHPC is selected member of the first pan-European HPC pilot Master program which involves a consortium of European universities as well as research/supercomputing centers and industrial partners. Every year, many of the MHPC students are returning students with industrial experience.
- *Master in Science Communication* (MCS). In collaboration with professionals in the field including very innovative courses such as in journalism and AI, in science and politics, and in data journalism.

Finally, SISSA has an outstanding experience in leading European Doctoral Networks and European Industrial Doctorate (EID), as well as Research Summer Schools.

Initiatives aimed at the broader education of SISSA students may be of interest to iNEST partners. We promote student's lead seminars and workshops such as the *Junior Maths Days* conference and specialized seminar series. Our students are also involved in the *SISSA 4 Schools* (S4S) initiative aimed at pupils of all ages which include welcoming pupils in SISSA to experience the life of scientists. This is part of a broader initiative in *Talent Valorisation and Development* providing a series of events and courses aimed at strengthening soft skills, including employability through interactions with industries. This initiative includes the programs:

- PHD4PMI and PHD4INNOVATION (Training learning by doing): students are challenged by industries to solve their innovation needs. The initiative is now being offered to all seven schools of excellence of Italy through the PRO3 program.
- Series of webinar training delivered by entrepreneurs, venture capitalists, and headhunters.

Soft skills training also includes one-to-one coaching with the talent valorisation one-to-one coaching sessions, Job Fairs and the JOIN program *Find job inspiration in SISSA Alumni's career stories*.

We also promote gender equality initiatives aimed at reversing the traditional imbalance in gender representation at academic and research levels in mathematics and physics with the Women in Maths and Women in Physics initiatives. Notably, over 20% of MHPC students are women, a much higher percentage than that found at national and international level in this sector which can be as low as 5%.

In the frame of Spoke 9, SISSA collaborates with OGS in developing a digital twin of the North Adriatic Sea. OGS, together with Cineca, the national supercomputing centre, established a training programme in the field of High Performance Computing (HPC) for applications in Earth Sciences, called "HPC Training and Research for Earth Sciences" (HPC-TRES), supported by the Ministry of Universities and Research (MUR). The main objectives of the programme are capacity building, the enhancement of human capital, and advanced training in the fields of Digital Twin Earth, Earth System modelling and numerical methods, the latter being considered a strategic transversal component for modelling. HPC-TRES co-funds training and research awards (scholarships, research grants, and PhDs) designed to contribute to the thematic research lines of the scientific plan of the HPC-TRES programme. Since 2015, HPC-TRES has co-funded almost 60 young researchers. For more details see <https://www.ogs.it/en/high-performance-computing-laboratory-hpc-tres>.

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An abstract collage background composed of various colored shapes and textures. The colors include red, orange, green, blue, yellow, dark blue, and white. The shapes are irregular and layered, creating a complex, multi-colored composition. The overall style is reminiscent of mid-century modern or pop art.

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